

PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF INDIAN HERBAL MEDICINAL PLANTS BY USING 3 DIFFERENT SOLVENT

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 31/05/2023

Available online

26/06/2023

Keywords

Traditional Medicine,
Pharmacological Activity,
Phytochemical Screening,
S. Cumini.

ABSTRACT

In this investigation, the anti-inflammatory, analgesic, sedative, and muscle-relaxing effects of the traditional Chinese medicine *Syzygium cumini* were evaluated, along with its many other pharmacological properties. One of these three solvents is used to extract the chemicals found in the jamun plant, including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, carbohydrates, and more. For the purpose of this review, information regarding the botany, traditional applications, phytochemical components, and pharmacological properties of *S. cumini* (L.) Skeels (jambolan) has been assembled. We looked up *Eugenia jambolana*, *S. cumini*, jambolan, common plum, and java plum in many internet databases. Anti-diabetic properties have been attributed to the plant ever since it was made available for commercial use several decades ago. The anti-diabetic properties of this plant have been the focus of research conducted by both traditional medicine practitioners and scientists over the course of the past four decades.

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Please cite this article in press as **Mateshwari Nandan et al.** *Phytochemical Study of Indian Herbal Medicinal Plants by Using 3 Different Solvent. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2023;13(06).*

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INTRODUCTION

This fruit is also referred to as the Java plum, Indian blackberry, black plum, and jamun. Other names for it include jambul, jambolao, and jamun. The scientific name for this plant is *Syzygium cumini* (L.). This species of plant is a member of the Myrtaceae family. In addition to the nations of its origin in South Asia (mainly Pakistan, India, Afghanistan, and Myanmar), and Pacific Asia (Indonesia, the Philippines, Hawaii, and Australia), commercial fruit production is also performed in Florida and Kenya [1]. This is in addition to the countries of its origin in South Asia. Before it falls off the tree, the fruit ripens from a greenish hue to a color that is somewhere between pink and crimson (see Figure 1).

Fig: 1 Fruit of *Syzygium cumini* (L.) [16].

The monsoon season in Asia, which runs from June to July, is often when the harvesting of jamun fruit begins, and it can persist for as long as forty days [1]. The succulent fruits produced by the *S. cumini* plant, which can range in size from 1.5 to 3.5 centimeters and have a flavor described as astringent [2]. The bitterness can be greatly mitigated by pickling, salting, and allowing the combination to sit undisturbed for at least an hour [3]. For the preparation of condiments like as jam and chutney, the fruits of the *S. cumini* tree can be used either fresh or cooked. The fruits can also be consumed in their natural, uncooked state. *S. cumini* juice can be used to produce a variety of refreshing summery recipes, including squash, sherbet, and syrup. Before adding water, sugar, citric acid, and sodium benzoate, the liquid extracted from the fruit is normally heated for ten minutes. This step is performed with the intention of preserving the fruit. Because of the seed's one-of-a-kind nutritional make-up, there is a possibility that it might be utilized in the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries [4]. Because they contain a significant amount of iron, the seeds are able to increase hemoglobin levels and purify the blood [5]. Because the seed contains a significant amount of iron, conditions such as anemia and jaundice can be avoided [6]. In addition, the calcium found in the seed can be used as a supplement by nursing mothers and pregnant women to assist them meet their required daily intake of calcium [7]. Because of its nutritious and practical features, the seed has been utilized in a broad variety of food products, including cookies, biscuits, chips, and wine [8]. The antioxidant capacity of the seed has been examined, and its utility in increasing the oxidative stability of a variety of food matrices has been proven by researchers [9]. As can be seen from their nutritional and phytochemical profiles, jamun seeds have the potential to become a new resource for the food and pharmaceutical industries in the very near future. This is evidenced by the fact that they contain a lot of antioxidants. Additionally, it increases knowledge of the probable hazards connected with the consumption of JS, which paves the route for future study to create a variety of functional meals based on jamun seeds or their extracts without compromising the safety of the food. The length of the core seed that is found within a jamun fruit can range anywhere from one centimeter to two centimeters [10]. Jamun contains a wide variety of phytochemicals, and every part of the plant, including the flower, fruit, seed, fruit pulp, leaves, and stem bark, possesses its own special significant bioactive components [11]. It is possible for the nutritional and phytochemical content of jamun fruit to fluctuate over time [12], depending on factors such as the fruit's age, environment, growing region, farming practices, and post-harvest treatment. The jamun fruit contains a somewhat high concentration of various vitamins and minerals, including ascorbic acid, thiamine, and niacin; potassium, calcium, salt, phosphorus, and iron; and various types of carbohydrates, including glucose, sucrose, fructose, and galactose. In addition to this, it is composed of protein, which includes free amino acids such as asparagine, alanine, glutamine, tyrosine, and cysteine. In addition to this, research [13] has demonstrated that jamun contains a variety of bioactive components that are advantageous to the health of individuals. The amount of phytochemicals (polyphenols, tannins, and gallic acid) that are present in jamun is the primary factor that determines its color, flavor, and scent [14]. According to research conducted in 2013 [15], jamun seed oil included a total of 32.2% oleic acid, 31.7% myristic acid, 16.1% linoleic acid, 6.5% stearic acid, 4.7% palmitic acid, 3.0% vernolic acid, 2.8% lauric acid, 1.8% sterculic acid, and 1.2% malvalic acid. In recent times, a number of different solvents have been utilized in the process of removing the fatty acids from jamun seeds.

The bulk of the fatty acids that were found in this analysis using hexane were oleic acid, linoleic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, linoleic acid, arachidic acid, eicosapentaenoic acid, erucic acid, myristic acid, docosahexaenoic acid, and lauric acid [16]. This particular plant species has significant quantities of a wide variety of bioactive compounds, including jambosine, quercetin, -sitosterol, gallic acid, guaiacol, resorcinol, p-coumaric acid, corilagin, ellagic acid, catechin, epicatechin, and tannic acid [17]. Jambosine is one of the most abundant of these compounds. Guaiacol and gallic acid are two examples of the compounds that fall within this category. The many parts of the jamun plant each have their own unique antioxidant capability, total flavonoid content (TFC), and total phenolic content (TPC). According to the findings of research carried out by Ali et al. [18], the skin of the Jamun fruit has a higher concentration of total polyphenolic compounds (mg GAE/g), total flavonoid compounds (mg quercetin/100 g), anthocyanin (mg cyanidin 3-rutinoside equivalent/100 g), and free-radical scavenging activity (%) than either the pulp or the seed. It's possible that the jamun seed's bioactivity was altered in some way by the solvent that was employed to extract it [18]. In addition, research conducted in the field has demonstrated that methanol is superior to methylene chloride when it comes to the process of extracting flavonoids [19]. Researchers Bajpai et al. [20] found that the seeds of this plant have a total phenolic content of 108.79 mg/g gallic acid equivalent and an antioxidant activity of 85.49 0.8%. These findings were based on their analysis of the seed.

MATERIAL & METHODS

We Searching From different sources like pubmed, Publon, Google Scholar, Searching criteria period Dec 2022-April 2023. *Syzygium cumini* Lin Species for Antioxidant Properties of their parts like leaves, stem, root.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Table 1 Phytochemical Screening of *Syzygium cumini* Leaves.

Phytochemical tests	Methanolic extract	Ethanol extracts	Aqueous extract
Molisch's test	+	+	-
Fehling test	-	+	+
Benedict test	-	+	+
Borntrager test	-	-	-
Biuret test	+	+	+
Ninhydrin test	+	+	+
Spot test	+	+	-
Saponification test	+	+	-
Lieberman burchard test	+	+	+
Mayer test	+	+	+
Wagner test	+	+	+
Hager test	+	+	+
Foam test	+	+	+
Ferric chloride test	+	+	+
Gelatin test	+	+	+
Lead acetate test	+	+	+
Alkaline test	+	-	+
Volatile test	+	-	+

Table 2: Phytochemical Screening of Syzygium cumini. Stem.

Phytochemical tests	Methanolic extract	Ethanol extracts	Aqueous extract
Molisch's test	+	+	-
Fehling test	-	+	+
Benedict test	-	+	-
Borntrager test	+	-	-
Biuret test	+	-	+
Ninhydrin test	+	+	+
Spot test	+	+	-
Saponification test	+	-	-
Lieberman burchard test	+	+	+
Mayer test	+	+	+
Wagner test	+	+	+
Hager test	+	+	+
Foam test	+	-	-
Ferric chloride test	-	+	+
Gelatin test	+	+	+
Lead acetate test	+	-	+
Alkaline test	+	-	+
Volatile test	+	-	+

Table 3 Phytochemical Screening of Syzygium cumini Root.

Phytochemical tests	Methanolic extract	Ethanol extracts	Aqueous extract
Molisch's test	+	+	-
Fehling test	-	+	+
Benedict test	-	+	-
Borntrager test	-	-	-
Biuret test	+	+	+
Ninhydrin test	+	+	+
Spot test	+	+	-
Saponification test	+	-	-
Lieberman burchard test	+	+	+
Mayer test	+	+	+
Wagner test	+	+	+
Hager test	+	+	+
Foam test	+	-	-
Ferric chloride test	-	+	+
Gelatin test	+	+	+
Lead acetate test	+	-	+
Alkaline test	+	-	+
Volatile test	+	-	+

Pharmacological Activity of Syzygium cumini Leaves[22]**Cardiovascular effects**

The addition of jamun to the diet had a beneficial effect on blood lipids, lowering cholesterol levels and the ratio of low density lipoprotein to high density lipoprotein by 12%. People who regularly consumed walnuts (both the oil and the kernel) were found to have higher levels of HDL cholesterol and apo A1 in their bodies, according to research that used a cross-sectional design.

CNS effects

Pentylenetetrazole (PTZ; 2 mg/ml/min) induced seizures in rats, which were used in this experiment to investigate the potential anticonvulsant effects of jamun kernel extract (WKE). Injection of WKE resulted in a considerable increase in the amount of PTZ required to produce the first myoclonic jerk (13.09 1.29 vs. 49.71 12.03 mg/kg; P0.05); this was due to the effects of WKE. It suggests that the anticonvulsant effect is related to signaling pathways other than benzodiazepine receptors that are mediated by gamma-aminobutyric acid.

Anti-cancer effect

In order to induce convulsions in rats, the drug pentylenetetrazole (PTZ; 2 mg/ml/min) was administered. The rats were then used in an experiment to determine whether or not jamun kernel extract (WKE) had any potential anticonvulsant effects. After receiving an injection of WKE, the threshold PTZ dose for inducing the first myoclonic jerk was considerably higher (13.09 1.29 vs. 49.71 12.03 mg/kg; P 0.05). This was determined by comparing the results of the two groups. According to the findings of this study, the anticonvulsant effect of benzodiazepines appears to be mediated through signalling pathways that are distinct from those that are regulated by benzodiazepines.

Antidiabetic effect

For the purpose of determining whether or not *Syzygium cumini* leaves are useful in treating diabetes type 1, streptozotocin-induced diabetes type 1 was induced in rats. After receiving treatment with an extract of *Juglans regia*, the patient's levels of blood sugar, glycosylated haemoglobin, low-density lipoprotein, triglycerides, and total cholesterol all significantly dropped, while the patient's levels of insulin and high-density lipoprotein rose.

Antioxidant effect

In vitro research was carried out to investigate the effect of walnut husk hydroalcoholic extract on the oxidation of serum LDL that was brought about by copper sulfate. At dosages of 0.2, 2, and 20 g/ml, respectively, the hydroalcoholic extract of walnut husk was reported to significantly lower serum LDL oxidation by 87%, 178%, and 202%, respectively.

Pharmacological Activity of *Syzygium cumini* Linn Root

Anti-fungal activity

It was determined whether or not the alcohol extract of *Syzygium cumini* L. stem bark was effective. In vitro testing found that it was efficient against a strain of the *Rhizoctonia solani* fungus that had been identified from broccoli, tomato, and chicken eggs. Extract of *Syzygium cumini*. reduced radial growth by 3.5 centimeters when the concentration of plant extract was 5%; this inhibition subsequently decreased to 0.4 centimeters when the concentration of plant extract was 20%.

Blood Concentration

An aqueous extract of the root bark of *Syzygium cumini* was used to study its potential effects on plasmatic coagulation, bleeding time, and platelet aggregation. It was found to have properties of both anticoagulation and platelet aggregation in its composition. The fibrinogen dose, the thrombin time, the prothrombin time, and the activated partial thromboplastin time are the parameters that describe the clotting process. *Syzygium cumini* extract was found to prevent platelet aggregation by a mechanism that was linked to the ADP-thrombin-collagen axis..

Anti inflammation activity

Research was conducted on the oil and kernel extract of *Syzygium cumini* to investigate its potential anti-inflammatory and anti-nociceptive properties. Linoleic acid was the factor that led to a reduction in blood sugar levels, as well as pain and inflammation. When the serum insulin levels were brought back up to normal, the glycated haemoglobin level also returned to normal. The combination of ethyl acetate and kernel extract led to an increase in insulin production while simultaneously bringing down blood sugar levels..

Anticancer Activity

Researchers found that *Syzygium cumini* has the ability to inhibit the growth of cancerous cells in the human breast and colon when they put it to the test against the survivability of human breast and colon cancer cells. Bromide of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium is used in the MTT assay, which counts the number of cancer cells that have survived. Walnut protein hydrolysates were subjected to in vitro testing on human breast and colon cancer cell lines. Results were positive. It would appear that chymotrypsin possesses potentially useful anti-cancer effects. Both the HT-29 colon cancer cell line and the MDA-MB 231 breast cancer cell line are effectively suppressed by chymotrypsin hydrolysate's inhibitory effects. In breast cancer cells, the peptide fraction caused a drop in cell proliferation of 631.73%, whereas in colon cancer cells it caused a decrease of 511.45%.

Pharmacological Activity of *Syzygium cumini* Stem[23]

Anxiolytic activity

When investigated for its anxiolytic effects on rodents, *Syzygium cumini* kernel hydroalcoholic extract showed promising results, indicating that the Omega-3 fatty acids found in walnuts may be responsible for this effect.

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidants prevent cell death and delay the aging process; fruits are an excellent source of antioxidants. In common with a great number of other fruits, are recognized for possessing a very high concentration of phytochemical antioxidants. These antioxidants protect cells from the damage that can be caused by free radicals. As a consequence of this, the antioxidant capability of the jamun tree in its entirety has been examined in great detail.

Antimicrobial Activity

It was discovered that extracts of *Syzygium cumini* made with chloroform and water were microbicidal against airborne bacteria, whereas extracts made with methanol had no effect whatsoever (42). By employing the disc diffusion method, researchers were able to detect antibacterial activity in Jamun leaf extract against acne-causing organisms that contribute to the development of acne. This finding suggests that Jamun leaf extract may be useful in the treatment of acne.

Chemical Composition

Anthocyanins, glucosides, ellagic acid, isoquercetin, kaemferol, and myrecetin are some of the components that can be found in jambolan. It has been demonstrated that the presence of ellagic acid in seed extract results in a 34.6% reduction in blood pressure [24]. There is also the possibility that the seeds contain the glycoside jambolin, which is also known as antimellin, as well as the alkaloid jamboline. The seeds have been shown to have a high concentration of flavonoids, which is a well-known antioxidant that is responsible for scavenging free radicals and having a protective effect on antioxidant enzymes [25]. In addition, the seeds have a high concentration of total phenolics, which have a powerful antioxidant activity [26], and they have a moderately high concentration of protein and calcium. Sugar, mineral salts, vitamins C and PP (which improves the health effects of vitamin C), anthocyanins, and flavonoids can all be found in high concentrations in Java plums [27]. In recent years, the jamun seed fatty acid extraction process has been carried out utilizing a variety of different solvents. The bulk of the fatty acids that were found in this analysis using hexane were oleic acid, linoleic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, linoleic acid, arachidic acid, eicosapentaenoic acid, erucic acid, myristic acid, docosahexaenoic acid, and lauric acid [28]. This kind of plant is rich in a wide variety of bioactive compounds, including jambosine, quercetin, -sitosterol, gallic acid, guaiacol, resorcinol, p-coumaric acid, corilagin, ellagic acid, catechin, epicatechin, and tannic acid, among others [29]. The total flavonoid concentration (TFC), the total phenolic content (TPC), and the antioxidant activity of various jamun components are all distinct from one another. According to the findings of a study that was carried out by Ali et al. [30], the skin of the jamun fruit has higher concentrations of total polyphenolic content (mg GAE/g), total flavonoid content (mg quercetin/100 g), anthocyanin (mg cyanidin 3-rutinoside equivalent/100 g), and free-radical scavenging capacity (%) than the pulp and the seed. The total phenolic content of the plant's seeds was determined to be 108.79 mg of gallic acid equivalent per gram, and their antioxidant activity was found to be 85.49 0.8%. [31]. Figure 2 provides a more in-depth examination of the bioactive components of jamun seed that are considered to be the most important. Natural products are becoming an increasingly popular, risk-free, and workable option as medical agents right now, particularly in countries that are still developing [32]. Ivy leaf, which is used as an expectorant, and silymarin, which is used as a hepatoprotective, are two examples of plant extracts and their individual components that are increasingly being used in the medical industry as therapeutic therapies. Researchers are interested in examining these possible medicinal plants to evaluate their conventional applications and claims as a result of the natural products' remarkable performance and noteworthy safety profile as therapeutic agents. This is due to the fact that natural products have a promising performance and noteworthy safety profile. [33]. In the current study, the pharmacological effects of *S. cumini*'s crude extract and the numerous fractions that it contains were analyzed. Traditional uses of *S. cumini* include the treatment of inflammation and discomfort, in addition to its use as a sedative and muscle relaxant [34]. At a greater dose of 500 mg/kg, *S. cumini* showed signs of moderate lethargy and a halt in locomotion; however, they did not pass away at the highest dose of 1000 mg/kg. The in vivo activity of the crude extracts and fractions was shown to be risk-free when administered at doses ranging from 25 to 500 mg/kg. The effectiveness of *S. cumini* extracts and fractions in reducing the edema brought on by carrageenan exposure was investigated. The crude methanolic extract of *S. cumini* was found to be the most effective at preventing paw edema, followed by the fractions generated via ethyl acetate, dichloromethane, chloroform, and n-hexane, respectively. The most effective fraction was the methanolic extract, followed by the ethyl acetate fraction, the dichloromethane fraction, the chloroform fraction, and finally the n-hexane fraction. There was a dose-dependent relationship between *S. cumini* extract's analgesic efficacy and all of its fractions. Prostaglandins (PGs), bradykinin, and histamine are all examples of inflammatory mediators that can be produced in response to carrageenan [35]. In the process of mediating pain, inflammation, and fever, PGs play a role that is disproportionately significant [36]. The ability of *S. cumini* to inhibit cyclo-oxygenase (COX) can cause changes in the intracellular cascades that are responsible for pain, inflammation, and fever. In addition to its ability to inhibit PGs, *S. cumini* possesses the sedative and muscle-relaxing properties that are indicative of its capability to influence a variety of other pharmacodynamic pathways[37]. This capacity was discovered independently of its ability to inhibit PGs. The extracts of *S. cumini* were especially helpful in easing the tension in the muscles and putting the body at ease[38]. It is believed that the chemical components of *S. cumini* maintain open anion neural channels, particularly chloride channels, which are required for the plant to have the sedative and muscle-relaxing effects that are attributed to it. Anion influx is caused by stimulation of gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors, which in turn leads to an increase in chloride inflow and leads to hyperpolarization of the neuronal membrane. In addition, these findings point to the possibility that the crude extract or one of its fractions may speed up the action of GABA neurotransmitters, which are the neurochemicals responsible for calming and relaxing the muscles [39]. Additional mechanistic investigations of *S. cumini*'s isolated components are required in order to pin down the precise process by which the fungus *S. cumini* exerts its effects[40].

Fig: 2 Bioactive compound present in jamun plants [37].

CONCLUSION

According to the preliminary phytochemical screening that was done on the three different extracts (methanol, ethanol, and aqueous), the methanolic extract of *Syzygium cumini* contained the most important phytoconstituents. The other two extracts were ethanolic and aqueous. The rising pharmacological relevance is further supported by the comparative antibacterial efficacy of the three extracts. Documentation of *Syzygium cumini* (jamun) and its constituents from the most current and most recent two years (December 2022 to April 2023). The essay mostly focused on the purported biological characteristics of this plant, both in vivo and in vitro, as well as its historical and medical applications. It has been established that extracting the many photochemicals that jamun contains is a highly efficient technique to treat a variety of pathological disorders in both rats and people. Jamun possesses a vast variety of photochemicals. Further research on people in the form of clinical trials is necessary for both long-term and preventative investigations. The physicochemical parameters of *Syzygium cumini* were investigated in this study in order to assess the performance and quality of the plant. It has been demonstrated that extracts of *Syzygium cumini* bark have both antibacterial and antifungal activities, making them effective against pathogenic bacteria and fungi. The results of this research provide credence to the theory that the bark of the *Syzygium cumini* tree can be beneficial in the treatment of a variety of diseases, particularly those that are prevalent in more rural settings.

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